

Floristic Composition and Diversity of Vascular Plant Species in the Char Kukri Mukri Mangrove Ecosystem of Bhola District, Bangladesh

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Abstract

The present study provides a comprehensive data regarding the species composition and diversity of vascular plants found in the Char Kukri-Mukri mangrove ecosystem of Bhola district, Bangladesh. It reveals the occurrence of 383 species belonging to 264 genera under 85 families of vascular plants, of which 48 species are mangroves and mangrove associates, and the rest of the 335 species are non-mangroves. The major plant groups, *viz.*, pteridophytes are represented by 11 species under 10 genera and six families; gymnosperms by two species under two genera and two families; magnoliopsida (dicotyledonous) by 278 species belonging to 194 genera and 60 families; and liliopsida by the rest of the 92 species under 59 genera and 17 families. Fabaceae is the largest dicot family with 43 species, and Poaceae with 30 species is recorded as the largest monocot family. Among the life-form categories, 198 (51.7%) species are recorded as herbs, followed by 98 (25.59%), 45 (11.75%), and 42 (10.97%) species those are recognized as trees, shrubs, and climbers, respectively. Seasonal variation in the average value of different diversity indices, including Simpson's, Shannon-Weiner, Margalef's, and McIntosh's diversity indices, representing the range from 0.59 to 0.81, 1.42 to 2.11, 1.67 to 2.39, and 0.38 to 0.61, respectively. The highest diversity indices values were always observed during monsoon season. Based on floristic status, the mangrove ecosystem of Char Kukri-Mukri Island seems to be of moderate quality. Nevertheless, in addition to the effects of climatic stressors, various human activities pose threats that increase the vulnerability of the study area. In this circumstance, the present study strongly recommends minimizing or stopping threat-causing activities, implementing effective conservation measures, and establishing regular monitoring to ensure future sustainability in the study area.

Keywords: *Floristic composition, Diversity, Char Kukri-Mukri Island, Mangrove Forest, Bhola district.*

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Introduction

Char Kukri-Mukri Island is in the southern part of Char Fasson upazila in the Bhola district of Bangladesh. The Island is separated from the mainland, facing the Bay of Bengal. The total area of the Island is about 40.38 km². The research area is located at offshore islands in bio-ecological zones which lie between 21°35' to 22°45' North latitudes and 90°15' to 92°05' East longitudes (Nishat *et al.*, 2002) with an elevation of 1.5 to 1.6 meters above sea level. According to local inhabitants, human settlement on this island began around 1930 during the British colonial period, but unfortunately, the 'Bhola Cyclone' hit this area during 1970 and swept the entire human population from the island. After the cyclone, in the year 1973/1974, people again migrated to the island and started fishing and cultivation. Bangladesh Forest Department started afforestation program using some mangrove species like, *Sonneratia apetala* (Keora), *Avicennia officinalis* (Baine), *Excoecaria agallocha* (Geoa), *Nypa fruticans* (Golpata) etc. in all around the Island. The forest area of this island is administered by Sadar Forest Beat and Char Patila Forest Beat under the Char Kukri-Mukri Forest Range of the Bhola Coastal Forest Division. The Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh declared 40 ha of this island's forest area (locally known as Kalir Char) as the Char Kukri-Mukri Wildlife Sanctuary on December 19, 1981 under the Bangladesh Wildlife (Preservation) Amendment Act of 1947 (Green, 1990) with an objective to protect its biodiversity. This area enjoys a tropical monsoon climate with an annual average rainfall of 2360 mm and an annual average temperature of about 22.15°C (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, 2011). The study area exhibits a semi-evergreen planted mangrove forest ecosystem with diverse microhabitats, harboring a heterogeneous assemblage of fauna and flora, including mangroves, mangrove-associates, and non-mangrove species.

The floristic composition provides basic information on the flora occurring within a specific geographic location, and diversity indicates the ecosystem quality of a particular geographical area, which is necessary for plant scientists, especially for plant ecologists, taxonomists, forest managers, and planners in understanding and conserving biodiversity. In spite of a very small area (147570 km², BBS, 2021), Bangladesh harbors about 5000 species of angiosperms (Khan, 1977), that is biodiversitically highly significant. But the detailed floristic investigation throughout this country has not yet been completed during over the last five decades, and most importantly, the floristic compositions in most of the areas of this country remain unrevealed or poorly understood. Out of the estimated species, a total of about 3902 species have been recorded from its geographical boundary during over the past two centuries through a variety of sporadically conducted floristic inventories (Roxburgh, 1814; Hooker, 1872-1897; Prain, 1903a, b; Uddin *et al.*, 1998; Khan and Huq, 2001; Rashid and Mia, 2001; Uddin *et al.*, 2003; Siddiqui *et al.*, 2007; Ahmed *et al.*, 2008-2009; Ahmed *et al.*, 2009; Islam *et al.*, 2009; Arefin *et al.*, 2011; Sultana, 2012; Rahman *et al.*, 2015; Tabassum, 2015; Haque *et al.*, 2018; Shetu *et al.*, 2018; Uddin and Hassan, 2018; Hossain *et al.*, 2020; Khanam *et al.*, 2020; Roy and Khan, 2020; Ashrafuzzaman and Sarwar, 2021; Hossain *et al.*, 2021; Khan *et al.*, 2021 a & b; Hossain *et al.*, 2022; Islam *et al.*, 2022; Shetu *et al.*, 2022; Hossain *et al.*, 2023; Islam *et al.*, 2024; Rahman *et al.*, 2023; Rani *et al.*, 2024; Khan and Rahman, 2025). Therefore, there is a great opportunity to investigate the detailed floristic information and diversity index in this area, where the information is still lacking.

The mangrove ecosystem in Bhola district is situated in the central coastal region of the country, which is mainly found in the Char Kukri-Mukri area. This ecosystem is one of the most productive and protective ecosystems, which provides a wide range of ecosystem goods and services. The mangrove ecosystem in Bhola district is more dynamic but highly vulnerable to both climatic (like sea level rise, cyclone, storm surge, coastal inundation, land erosion etc.) and anthropogenic (like economic development, unplanned tourisms, excessive grazing etc.) stressors. As a result, this ecosystem has been gradually reduced and lost its potential functions, productivity, and biodiversity. Although a taxonomic study on the angiosperm flora of this area was reported by Uddin and Abiabdullah (2016), but a good

number of important plant species were not listed in their finding. Moreover, the information regarding the floristic diversity of this mangrove ecosystem is still lacking. Hence, the present study has been conducted on detailed floristic composition and diversity of the Char Kukri-Mukri mangrove ecosystem to fulfill the lacunae.

Materials and Methods

Field surveys were conducted throughout the study area during three different seasons (i.e., monsoon, winter and summer) from July 2023 to December 2024. To analyze the floristic composition and prepare a comprehensive checklist, all vascular plants observed in study area were collected following standard quadrat method (Braun-Blanquet, 1932; Raunkiaer, 1934; Barker, 2001) and walk-through method (Junaid, 2018). For quantitative estimation, the study area was divided into eight representative sites on the basis of forest administrative units, geo-spatial locations, topographic features, habitats and vegetation patterns, which were recognized as site 1, site 2, site 3, site 4, site 5, site 6, site 7, and site 8 (Figure 1). On the basis of the species-area-curve method (Cain, 1938), the quadrat size of 2m × 2m, 5m × 5m and 10m × 10m were standardized and applied for herbaceous, shrubby and tree species, respectively to collect the vegetation samples. In each selected site, nine quadrats of three different size were applied for the floristic investigation.

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area Showing Study Sites of the Char Kukri-Mukri Mangrove Forest

Source: Bhuiyan *et al.*, 2025

Freshly collected plant specimens were processed, dried, and preserved following standard herbarium techniques (Bridson and Forman, 1989; Singh and Subramaniam, 2008). Identification of the specimens and verification of the nomenclatural information has been completed through consulting taxonomic descriptions and keys available in the relevant literature (Hooker, 1872-1897; Prain, 1903a, b; Wu and Raven, 1994-2001; Wu *et al.*, 1999-2013; The Plant List, 2013; Rahman *et al.*, 2015; Khan *et al.*, 2021; Hossain *et al.*, 2021 and 2022; Islam *et al.*, 2022; Hassler, 1994 – 2025; POWO, 2025; TROPICOS, 2025), and by matching with the respective voucher specimens preserved in Plant Ecology and Environment Laboratory. The families of pteridophytes, gymnosperms, and angiosperms have been arranged following the widely used classification systems of Pichi (1977), Kramer and Green (1990), and Cronquist (1988), respectively. The APG IV System (Angiosperm Phylogeny Group, 2016) has been used to place the families that are not included in Cronquist (1988). On the other hand, the genera and species under each

family are listed alphabetically. True mangrove and mangrove-associated plant species were recognized following FAO (2007), Giesen *et al.* (2007), and Rahman *et al.* (2015).

Floristic diversity indices were estimated using Simpson's diversity index (Simpson, 1949), Shannon-Wiener diversity index (Shannon, 1948), Margalef's index (Margalef, 1957) and McIntosh Diversity Index (McIntosh, 1967) using the following formulae respectively.

Simpson's diversity index

$$1-D = 1 - \frac{\sum n(n-1)}{N(N-1)} \quad (1)$$

Where, N is the total number of individuals of all species,

n is the total number of individuals of a particular species

Shannon-Weiner Diversity Index,

$$H' = -\sum p_i \ln p_i \quad (2)$$

Where, p_i is the proportion of observations found in category i ,

\ln is the natural logarithm

Margalef's Diversity Index,

$$D_{mar} = \frac{S-1}{\ln N} \quad (3)$$

Where, S is the total number of recorded species,

N is the total number of individuals of all recorded species

McIntosh Diversity Index,

$$D_{mc} = \frac{N-U}{N-\sqrt{N}} \quad (4)$$

Where, N is the total no. of individuals,

U is the $\sqrt{\sum n_i^2}$, n_i is the no. of individual of i th species.

Results

The present study records the occurrence of 383 species belonging to 264 genera under 85 families of vascular plants in the Char Kukri Mukri mangrove ecosystem of Bhola district, of which 48 (12.53%) species are mangroves and mangrove associates, and the rest of the 335 (87.47%) species are non-mangroves. In this study, the major plant groups, *viz.*, pteridophytes are represented by 11 species under

10 genera and six families, gymnosperms by two species under two genera and two families, magnoliopsida (dicotyledonous) by 278 species belonging to 194 genera and 60 families that constituted 72.58% of the vascular flora of the study area, and liliopsida by rest of the 92 species under 58 genera and 17 families, which comprised 24.02% of this flora (Table-1). Thelypteridaceae with three species representing the largest family of pteridophyte, which is followed by Pteridaceae, Polypodiaceae, and Marsileaceae with two species each. The rest of each family, Athyriaceae and Blechnaceae represented by a single species. The two Gymnosperm families, Araucariaceae and Cupressaceae, are represented by only one species each. Among the dicotyledonous families, Fabaceae with 43 species is recorded as the largest family, which is followed by Asteraceae with 17 species, Malvaceae with 17 species, Acanthaceae with 13 species, and Euphorbiaceae with 12 species. In monocotyledonous families, Poaceae with 30 species is recorded as the largest family, which is followed by Cyperaceae with 24 species, Arecaceae with 7 species, Araceae with 6 species, and Amaryllidaceae with 5 species.

Table 1. Checklist of Vascular Flora in the Char Kukri-Mukri Mangrove Ecosystem of Bhola District, Bangladesh

Scientific name	Local name	Habit	Habitat	RSE
PTERIDOPHYTA Schimp.				
Marsileaceae Mirb.				
<i>Marsilea minuta</i> L.	Shushni shak	Herb	Wtl	AR 0494
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	Shushni shak	Herb	Wtl	AR 0356
Pteridaceae E.D.M. Kirchn.				
<i>Acrostichum aureum</i> L.	Tigerfern	Herb	Wl, Cs, Rs	AR 0471
<i>Ceratopteris thalictroides</i> (L.) Brongn.	Panishak	Herb	Wtl	AR 0188
Polypodiaceae J. Presl & C. Presl				
<i>Drynaria quercifolia</i> (L.) J. Sm.	Pankhiraj	Herb	Wl	AR 0459
<i>Microsorium punctatum</i> (L.) Copel.	Patra dehkia	Herb	Wl	AR 0260
Blechnaceae Newman				
<i>Stenochlaena palustris</i> (Burm. f.) Bedd.	Dhekialota	Climber	Fl, Rs, Wl	AR 0502
Thelypteridaceae Ching ex Pic. Serm.				
<i>Ampelopteris prolifera</i> (Retz.) Copel.	Dhekia shak	Herb	Rs, Cs, Hs	AR 0004
<i>Christella crinipes</i> (Hook.) Holttum	-	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0351
<i>Thelypteris dentata</i> (Forssk.) E.P. St. John	-	Herb	Rs, Hs, Wl	AR 0469
Athyriaceae Alston				
<i>Diplazium esculentum</i> (Retz.) Sw.	Dheki shak	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0398
GYMNOSPERMS Prantl				
Araucariaceae Henkel & W. Hochst.				
<i>Araucaria heterophylla</i> (Salisb.) Franco.	Australian Pine	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0302
Cupressaceae Gray				
<i>Platycladus orientalis</i> (L.) Franco	Patajhau	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0215
MAGNOLIOPSIDA Brongn.				
Annonaceae Juss.				
<i>Annona reticulata</i> L.	Ata phal	Tree	Fl, Hs	AR 0429
<i>A. squamosa</i> L.	Ata phal	Tree	Hs	AR 0028
Piperaceae Giseke				
<i>Peperomia pellucida</i> (L.) Kunth	Dipto luci pata	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0132
Nymphaeaceae Salisb.				
<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i> Burm. f.	Nilshapla	Herb	Wtl	AR 0493
<i>N. pubescens</i> Willd.	Sada Shapla	Herb	Wtl	AR 0255
<i>N. rubra</i> Roxb. ex Salisb.	Lalshapla	Herb	Wtl	AR 0023
Menispermaceae Juss.				
<i>Stephania japonica</i> (Thunb.) Miers	Muchchanilata	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0156
<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers ex Hook. f. & Thomson	Gulanca	Climber	Hs, Rs	AR 0195
<i>Tinospora sinensis</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Padma Gulanca	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0289

Cannabaceae Martinov				
<i>Trema orientale</i> (L.) Blume	Jhigni	Tree	Rs	AR 0020
Moraceae Gaudich.				
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Kathal	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0317
<i>A. lacucha</i> Buch.-Ham. ex D. Don	Dewa	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0015
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Bot	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0120
<i>F. hispida</i> L. f.	Dumur	Tree	Cs, Rs	AR 0473
<i>F. racemosa</i> L.	Jogdumur	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0017
<i>F. religiosa</i> L.	Ashawatth	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0031
<i>F. rumpii</i> L.	Pakur	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0198
Urticaceae Juss.				
<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i> (L.) Benn. & R. Br.	Kularuki	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0333
Casuarinaceae R.Br.				
<i>Casuarina equisetifolia</i> L.	Jhau	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0461
Amaranthaceae Juss.				
<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Apang	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0303
<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i> (Mart.) Griseb	Helencha	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0353
<i>A. pungens</i> Kunth	Salanchi shak	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0050
<i>A. sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br. Ex DC.	Haincha shak	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0234
<i>A. villosa</i> Kunth	Moti shak	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0424
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Kata notey	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0316
<i>A. tricolor</i> L.	Lal shak	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0322
<i>A. viridis</i> L.	Notey shak	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0217
<i>Celosia argentea</i> L. f. <i>cristata</i> (L.) Schinz	Morogful	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0241
<i>C. argentea</i> L.	Morogful	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0258
Portulacaceae Juss.				
<i>Portulaca grandiflora</i> Hook.	Time ful	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0169
<i>P. oleracea</i> L.	Nunia shak	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0244
Basellaceae Raf.				
<i>Basella alba</i> L.	Puishak	Climber	Hs, Af	AR 0430
Molluginaceae Bartl.				
<i>Glinus oppositifolius</i> (L.) Aug. DC.	Gima shak	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0339
Polygonaceae Juss.				
<i>Persicaria glabra</i> (Willd.) M. Gómez	-	Herb	Cs, Rs, Wtl	AR 0497
<i>P. hydropiper</i> (L.) Opiz	Bishkatali	Herb	Cs, Rs, Wtl	AR 0378
<i>Polygonum flaccidum</i> Meisn.	Horin bon	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0362
<i>P. plebeium</i> R. Br.	Chimti shak	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0043
Dilleniaceae Salisb.				
<i>Dillenia indica</i> L.	Chalta	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0007
Clusiaceae Lindl.				
<i>Garcinia cowa</i> Roxb.	Kao	Tree	Hs	AR 0282
Elaeocarpaceae Juss.				
<i>Elaeocarpus tectorius</i> (Lour.) Poir.	Jolpai	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0391
Malvaceae Juss.				
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i> (L.) Moench	Bendi	Herb	Hs, Af	AR 0372
<i>A. moschatus</i> (L.) Medik.	Bonderos	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0130
<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Indian abutilon	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0409
<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Shimul	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0252
<i>Brownlowia tersa</i> (L.) Kosterm.	Lata Sundari	Shrub	Wl, Cs	AR 0417
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Shewt Shimul	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0162
<i>Corchorus capsularis</i> L.	Deshi pat	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0422
<i>C. olitorius</i> L.	Toshapat	Herb	Cs, Af	AR 0018
<i>Heritiera fomes</i> Buch.-Ham.	Sundari	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0002
<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Joba	Shrub	Hs	AR 0346
<i>H. tiliaceus</i> L.	Chelwa	Shrub	Wl, Cs, Rs	AR 0466
<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm. f.	Berela	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0444
<i>S. cordifolia</i> L.	Berela	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0006

<i>S. rhombifolia</i> L.	Shetberela	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0319
<i>Sterculia foetida</i> L.	Jongli badam	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0306
<i>Thespesia populnea</i> (L.) Sol. ex Corrêa	Shon boloi	Tree	Cs, Wl	AR 0157
<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	Bon okra	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0358
Lecythidaceae A. Rich.				
<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Hijol	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0296
Tamaricaceae Link				
<i>Tamarix indica</i> Willd.	Nuinnajhau	Shrub	Wl	AR 0265
Caricaceae Dumort.				
<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Pepe	Shrub	Hs	AR 0203
Cucurbitaceae Juss.				
<i>Benincasa hispida</i> (Thunb.) Cogn.	Chalkumra	Climber	Hs, Af	AR 0204
<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt	Telakucha	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0116
<i>Cucurbita maxima</i> Duchesne	Misti kumra	Climber	Hs, Rs	AR 0218
<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i> (Molina) Standl.	Lao	Climber	Hs, Af	AR 0053
<i>Luffa acutangula</i> Roxb.	Jinga	Climber	Af, Hs	AR 0256
<i>L. cylindrica</i> M.Roem.	Dundul	Climber	Af, Hs	AR 0499
<i>Momordica cochinchinensis</i> (Lour.) Spreng.	Buno kakrol	Climber	Rs	AR 0103
<i>Trichosanthes cucumerina</i> L.	Chichinga	Climber	Af, Hs	AR 0041
<i>T. dioica</i> Roxb.	Potol	Climber	Af, Hs	AR 0021
Salicaceae Mirb.				
<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm. f.) Merr.	Boichi	Shrub	Fl, Hs	AR 0376
Capparaceae Juss.				
<i>Crateva magna</i> (Lour.) DC.	Borun	Tree	Wl	AR 0152
Brassicaceae Burnett				
<i>Raphanus sativus</i> L.	Mulashak	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0009
<i>Rorippa indica</i> (L.) Hiern	Rorippa	Herb	Rs	AR 0119
Moringaceae Martinov				
<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Shajna	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0078
Ebenaceae Gürke				
<i>Diospyros blancoi</i> A. DC.	Bilatigab	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0058
<i>D. malabarica</i> (Desr.) Kostel.	Deshigab	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0097
Primulaceae Batsch				
<i>Aegiceras corniculatum</i> (L.) Blanco	Kalshi	Shrub	Wl, Cs	AR 0321
Crassulaceae J. St.-Hil.				
<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Lam.) Kurz	Pathorkuchi	Herb	Hs	AR 0411
Fabaceae Lindl.				
<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> A. Cunn. ex Benth. & Hook.	Akashmoni	Tree	Rs, Hs,	AR 0250
<i>A. catechu</i> (L.f.) Willd.	Catechu	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0127
<i>A. mangium</i> Willd.	Belgium	Tree	Rs	AR 0262
<i>A. nilotica</i> (L.) Willd. ex Delile	Babla	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0463
<i>Adenanthera paronina</i> L.	Lalchandon	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0019
<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.) Benth. & Hook.	Shilkoroi	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0057
<i>A. procera</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Sadakoroi	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0126
<i>A. richardiana</i> (Voigt.) King & Prain	Chambul	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0290
<i>A. saman</i> (Jack.) Merr.	Botkoroi	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0330
<i>Alysicarpus rugosus</i> (Willd.) DC.	Red moneywort	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0432
<i>Brachypterum scandens</i> (Roxb.) Benth	Mohajoni lata	Climber	Wl, Cs	AR 0331
<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i> (L.) Roxb.	Nata	Climber	Rs, Cs	AR 0011
<i>C. crista</i> L.	Kutum kata	Climber	Rs, Cs	AR 0115
<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Merr.	Orhor	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0470
<i>Canavalia ensiformis</i> (L.) DC.	Makhan shim	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0342
<i>C. gladiata</i> (Jacq.) DC.	Moushim	Climber	Rs, Rs	AR 0395
<i>C. maritima</i> Hiern	Dariashim	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0332
<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Sonalu	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0291
<i>Centrosoma pubescens</i> Benth.	Centro	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0075
<i>Clitoria turnetea</i> L.	Aparajita	Climber	Hs	AR 0213

<i>Crotalaria pallida</i> Aiton	Junjuni	Herb	Rs, Sd	AR 0490
<i>Cynometra ramiflora</i> L.	Singra	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0073
<i>Dalbergia candenatensis</i> (Dennst.) Prain	Chand lata	Climber	Wl, Cs	AR 0419
<i>D. sissoo</i> Roxb. ex DC.	Shishu	Tree	Rs	AR 0016
<i>D. spinosa</i> Roxb.	Tamu	Climber	Wl, Cs	AR 0202
<i>Derris trifoliata</i> Lour.	Kalilota	Climber	Wl, Cs	AR 0276
<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	Kudaliya	Herb	Fl, Cs	AR 0104
<i>Erythrina stricta</i> Roxb.	Raktamandar	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0024
<i>E. ovalifolia</i> Roxb.	Mandar	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0465
<i>Lablab purpureus</i> (L.) Sweet	Seem	Climber	Hs, Af	AR 0026
<i>Lathyrus sativus</i> L.	Khesari	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0035
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i> (Lam.) de Wit	Epilepil	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0151
<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth.	Khaia babla	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0484
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Koroj	Tree	Rs, Wl, Cs	AR 0039
<i>Psophocarpus tetragonolobus</i> (L.) DC.	Wingseem	Climber	Hs, Rs	AR 0355
<i>Senna alata</i> (L.) Roxb.	Dadmordan	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0197
<i>S. occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	Kolkasunda	Herb	Rs	AR 0049
<i>S. siamea</i> (Lam.) H.S. Irwin & Barneby	Minjiri	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0033
<i>S. tora</i> (L.) Roxb.	Bon chakunda	Herb	Rs	AR 0114
<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L.) Poir.	Bok ful	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0334
<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Tetul	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0122
<i>Vigna adenantha</i> (G. Mey.) Maréchal, Mascherpa & Stainier	Bon borboti	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0027
<i>V. unguiculata</i> (L.) Walp.	Borboti	Climber	Hs, Rs, Af	AR 0223
Lythraceae J. St.-Hil.				
<i>Ammannia multiflora</i> Roxb.	-	Herb	Fl, Rs	AR 0392
<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i> (L.) Pers.	Jarul	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0327
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.	Mehendi	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0034
<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	Dalim	Shrub	Hs	AR 0269
<i>Rotala ramosior</i> (L.) Koehne	-	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0253
<i>Sonneratia apetala</i> Banks	Keora	Tree	Wl	AR 0142
<i>S. caseolaris</i> (L.) Engl.	Soilla	Tree	Cs, Wl	AR 0387
Myrtaceae Juss.				
<i>Eucalyptus camaldulensis</i> Dehnh.	Eucalyptus	Tree	Rs	AR 0338
<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Peara	Tree	Hs	AR 0325
<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Kalojam	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0010
<i>S. fruticosum</i> Roxb. ex DC.	Bhutijam	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0451
<i>S. malaccense</i> (L.) Merr. & L.M. Perry	Jamrul	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0165
<i>S. samarangense</i> (Blume) Merr. & L.M. Perry	Golapjam	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0113
Onagraceae Juss.				
<i>Ludwigia byssopifolia</i> (G. Don) Exell	Panilong	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0498
<i>L. repens</i> J.R. Forst.	Molsi	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0112
Combretaceae R.Br.				
<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight & Arn.	Arjun	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0141
<i>T. bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Bohera	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0001
<i>T. catappa</i> L.	Kath badam	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0219
<i>T. chebula</i> Retz.	Haritoki	Tree	Hs	AR 0354
Rhizophoraceae Pers.				
<i>Bruguiera sexangula</i> (Lour.) Poir.	Sobuj Kakra	Tree	Wl	AR 0196
<i>Ceriops decandra</i> (Griff.) Ding Hou	Goran	Tree	Wl	AR 0418
Euphorbiaceae Juss.				
<i>Codiaeum variegatum</i> (L.) Rumph. ex A. Juss.	Patabahar	Shrub	Hs	AR 0379
<i>Croton bonplandianus</i> Baill.	Bantulshi	Herb	Rs	AR 0320
<i>Chrozophora plicata</i> (Vahl) A. Juss. ex Spreng.	Khudifora	Herb	Rs	AR 0005
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Dudhia	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0347
<i>E. thymifolia</i> L.	Dudhia	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0036
<i>E. tirucalli</i> L.	Dudhraj	Herb	Rs, Af, Fl	AR 0179
<i>Excoecaria agallocha</i> L.	Gewa	Tree	Wl	AR 0172

<i>Pedilanthus tithymaloides</i> (L.) Poit.	Chita	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0045
<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Venna	Shrub	Hs, Sd, Rs	AR 0413
<i>Shirakiopsis indica</i> (Willd.) Esser	Harua	Tree	Cs, Wl	AR 0267
<i>Trenia nudiflora</i> L.	Pitali	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0449
<i>T. polycarpa</i> Benth. & Hook. f.	Pitali	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0161
Phyllanthaceae Martinov				
<i>Breynia retusa</i> (Dennst.) Alston	Sitki	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0399
<i>Flueggea virosa</i> (Roxb. ex Willd.) Voigt	Chitka lota	Shrub	Rs, Fl	AR 0013
<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Amloki	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0088
<i>P. niruri</i> L.	Bhui amla	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0155
<i>P. reticulatus</i> Poir.	Sitki	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0390
<i>P. urinaria</i> L.	Hazar moni	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0287
Rhamnaceae Juss.				
<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Lam.	Boroi	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0090
Vitaceae Juss.				
<i>Cayratia maritima</i> Jackes	-	Climber	Cs, Rs	AR 0468
<i>C. trifolia</i> (L.) Domin	Amal-lata	Climber	Cs, Wl	AR 0464
Sapindaceae Juss.				
<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Lota futki	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0477
<i>Lepisanthes rubiginosa</i> (Roxb.) Leenh	Chagalguti	Tree	Rs, Wl	AR 0397
<i>L. senegalensis</i> (Juss. ex Poir.) Leenh.	Gotaharina	Tree	Rs, Wl	AR 0474
<i>Litchi chinensis</i> Sonn.	Lichu	Tree	Hs	AR 0149
Anacardiaceae R.Br.				
<i>Lannea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.) Merr.	Bhadi	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0297
<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Aam	Tree	Hs	AR 0125
<i>Spondias dulcis</i> Parkinson	Bilati amra	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0014
Meliaceae Juss.				
<i>Aglia cucullata</i> (Roxb.) Pellegr.	Amur	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0216
<i>Aphanamixis polystachya</i> (Wall.) R. N. Parker.	Pithraj	Tree	Hs	AR 0066
<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A. Juss.	Neem	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0238
<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	Goraneem	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0164
<i>Svietenia mahagoni</i> (L.) Jacq.	Mehagoni	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0313
<i>Toona ciliata</i> M. Roem.	Toon	Tree	Rs	AR 0340
<i>Xylocarpus granatum</i> J. Koenig	Dhundal	Tree	Cs, Wl	AR 0405
<i>X. moluccensis</i> (Lam.) M. Roem.	Posur	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0193
Rutaceae Juss.				
<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) corr.	Bel	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0445
<i>Citrus aurantifolia</i> (Christm.) Swingle	Lebu	Shrub	Hs	AR 0377
<i>C. maxima</i> (Burm.) Merr.	Jambura	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0285
<i>Glycosmis pentaphylla</i> (Retz.) DC.	Datmajon	Herb	Rs	AR 0063
Oxalidaceae R.Br.				
<i>Averrhoa carambola</i> L.	Kamranga	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0457
<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Amrul	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0194
Araliaceae Juss.				
<i>Hydrocotyle vulgaris</i> L.	Coin Plant	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0214
<i>Polyscias scutellaria</i> (Burm. f.) Fosberg	-	Shrub	Hs	AR 0199
Apiaceae Lindl.				
<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urb.	Thankuni pata	Herb	Rs, Af, Hs	AR 0099
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> L.	Dhoniya	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0038
<i>Eryngium foetidum</i> L.	Bilatidoinna	Herb	Hs, Af	AR 0174
Apocynaceae Juss.				
<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton) R. Br.	Akand	Shrub	Rs	AR 0275
<i>Cerbera manghas</i> L.	Dhakur	Tree	Wl, Rs, Cs	AR 0134
<i>Dregea volubilis</i> (L. f.) Benth. ex Hook. f.	Tita kunga	Climber	Rs	AR 0080
<i>Plumeria alba</i> L.	Kathgolap	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0286
<i>Nerium indicum</i> Mill.	Nerium	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0314
<i>Parsonsia alboflavescens</i> (Dennst.) Mabb.	-	Climber	Rs	AR 0375

<i>Sarcobolus globosus</i> Wall.	Baoli-lota	Climber	Wl, Cs	AR 0003
<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Roem. & Schult.	Togor	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0074
<i>Tylophora indica</i> (Burm. f.) Merr.	Antamul	Climber	Af, Hs	AR 0101
Solanaceae Juss.				
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i> L.	Morich	Shrub	Hs, Af	AR 0284
<i>Nicotiana plumbaginifolia</i> Viv.	Bon tamak	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0396
<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	Bon tepari	Herb	Rs	AR 0277
<i>P. peruviana</i> L.	Tepari	Herb	Rs	AR 0433
<i>Solanum indicum</i> L.	Futki begun	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0288
<i>S. lycopersicum</i> L.	Bilati begun	Herb	Hs, Af	AR 0200
<i>S. melogena</i> L.	Begun	Herb	Hs, Af, Rs	AR 0138
<i>S. nigrum</i> L.	Titbegun	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0308
<i>S. torvum</i> Sw.	Bon begun	Herb	Rs	AR 0089
<i>S. virginianum</i> L.	Kantikari begun	Herb	Rs	AR 0123
Convolvulaceae Juss.				
<i>Camonea vitifolia</i> (Burm. f.) Simões & Staples	-	Shrub	Rs	AR 0408
<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Shwarnalata	Climber	Rs	AR 0447
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forssk.	Kolmi	Herb	Hs, Wtl	AR 0037
<i>I. batatas</i> (L.) Lam.	Mistialu	Climber	Hs, Rs, Wtl	AR 0143
<i>I. fistulosa</i> Mart. ex Choisy	Dolkolmi	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0166
<i>I. littoralis</i> Blume	-	Climber	Cs, Rs	AR 0044
<i>I. pes-caprae</i> (L.) R. Br.	Sagorlota	Herb	Sd	AR 0491
<i>Merremia umbellata</i> (L.) Hallier f.	Merremia	Climber	Rs	AR 0139
<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso	Dudh kolmi	Climber	Rs, Af, Wtl	AR 0042
Hydroleaceae R.Br. ex Edwards				
<i>Hydrolea zeylanica</i> (L.) Vahl	Kasschra	Herb	Af	AR 0350
Boraginaceae Juss.				
<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G. Forst.	Bohul	Tree	Wl	AR 0212
<i>Heliotropium curassavicum</i> L.	Nuna hatisur	Herb	Af, Rs, Hs	AR 0040
<i>H. indicum</i> L.	Hatisur	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0323
Verbenaceae J. St.-Hil.				
<i>Lippia alba</i> (Mill.) N.E. Br. ex Britton & P. Wilson	Motmotia	Herb	Rs, Wl	AR 0437
<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	Bhui okra	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0077
<i>Stachytarpheta cayennensis</i> (Rich.) Vahl	Niler jhi	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0274
Lamiaceae Martinov				
<i>Clerodendrum indicum</i> (L.) Kuntze	Bamon hati	Shrub	Rs	AR 0189
<i>C. infortunatum</i> L.	Bhat	Herb	Rs	AR 0220
<i>Gmelina arborea</i> Roxb. ex Sm.	Gamar	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0228
<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit.	Tokma	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0129
<i>Ocimum americanum</i> L.	Kalo tulsi	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0294
<i>O. sanctum</i> L.	Tulsi	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0128
<i>Premna serratifolia</i> Blanco	Goniari	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0487
<i>Vitex trifolia</i> L.	Nilnishinda	Shrub	Rs, Wl	AR 0343
<i>Volkameria inermis</i> L.	Bon jhui	Shrub	Cs, Wl,	AR 0440
Plantaginaceae Juss.				
<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Edwall	Brammi Shak	Herb	Wl, Rs, Cs, Wtl	AR 0482
<i>Mecardonia procumbens</i> (Mill.) Small	Mikardan	Herb	Fl	AR 0107
<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	Chinipata	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0160
Linderniaceae Borsch, Kai Müll. & Eb. Fisch.				
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Sada pani ghas	Herb	Wtl, Fl, Af	AR 0147
<i>L. crustacea</i> (L.) F. Muell.	-	Herb	Wtl, Fl	AR 0245
<i>L. procumbens</i> (Krock.) Philcox	-	Herb	Wtl, Fl	AR 0186
<i>L. rotundifolia</i> (L.) Alston	-	Herb	Wtl, Fl	AR 0489
Acanthaceae Juss.				
<i>Acanthus ilicifolius</i> L.	Hargoza	Shrub	Wl, Cs	AR 0025
<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm. f.) Wall.	Kalomegh	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0209

<i>Avicennia marina</i> (Forssk.) Vierh	Moricha Bain	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0076
<i>A. officinalis</i> L.	Bain	Tree	Wl, Cs	AR 0187
<i>Hemigraphis birta</i> T. Anderson	Buripana	Herb	Rs, Hs, Af	AR 0224
<i>Hygrophila phlomooides</i> Nees	-	Herb	Rs, Fl, Af	AR 0393
<i>H. polysperma</i> (Roxb.) T. Anderson	Alaikalai	Herb	Fl, Af	AR 0055
<i>H. salicifolia</i> (Vahl) Nees	Kakmasha	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0270
<i>Justicia adhatoda</i> L.	Bashak	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0434
<i>J. gendarussa</i> Burm. f.	Justicia	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0008
<i>Nelsonia canescens</i> (Lam.) Spreng.	Poramul	Herb	Rs	AR 0185
<i>Ruelia tuberosa</i> L.	Potpoti	Herb	Rs	AR 0163
<i>Rungia pectinata</i> (L.) Nees	Pindi	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0012
Bignoniaceae Juss.				
<i>Dolichandrone spathacea</i> (L. f.) Baillon ex Schumann	Ghorshingha	Tree	Wl, Rs	AR 0105
Lentibulariaceae Rich.				
<i>Utricularia excolete</i> R. Br.	Jhaji	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0140
Rubiaceae Juss.				
<i>Dentella repens</i> (L.) J.R. Forst. & G. Forst.	Bhuiyat	Herb	Af	AR 0472
<i>Gardenia jasminoides</i> J. Ellis	Gondhoraj	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0478
<i>Ixora coccinea</i> L.	Rongon	Shrub	Hs	AR 0100
<i>Morinda citrifolia</i> L.	Banach	Shrub	Rs, Hs	AR 0173
<i>Neolamarckia cadamba</i> (Roxb.) Bosser	Kadam	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0448
Asteraceae Bercht. & J. Presl				
<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> L.	Fulkuri	Herb	Rs	AR 0318
<i>Blumea lacera</i> (Burm. f.) DC.	Healmutra	Herb	Rs, Fl, Cs	AR 0326
<i>Cotula hemisphaerica</i> (Roxb.) Wall. ex Benth.	Babui	Herb	Af	AR 0357
<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H. Rob.	Kukshim	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0263
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Keshraj	Herb	Af, Rs, Hs	AR 0236
<i>Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum</i> (L.) Hilliard & B.L.Burt	Dholipui	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0062
<i>Grangea maderaspatana</i> (L.) Poir.	Nemuti	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0428
<i>Launaea asplenifolia</i> Hook. f.	-	Herb	Rs	AR 0059
<i>Mikania cordata</i> (Burm.f.) B.L.Rob.	Asamlata	Climber	Rs, Hs	AR 0178
<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Murmuriya	Herb	Fl, Rs	AR 0293
<i>Spilanthes acmella</i> Hutch. & Dalziel	Bongadha	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0389
<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Surya-kanya	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0133
<i>Tagetes patula</i> L.	Gada	Herb	Hs	AR 0337
<i>Wedelia calendulacea</i> Rich.	Kesuria	Herb	Wl, Rs	AR 0344
<i>W. longifolia</i> Mart. ex Baker	-	Herb	Wl, Rs, Cs	AR 0065
<i>Wollastonia biflora</i> (L.) DC.	-	Shrub	Cs, Wl	AR 0420
<i>Xanthium indicum</i> J. Koenig ex Roxb.	Ghagra	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0336
Calophyllaceae J. Agardh				
<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> L.	Punnag	Tree	Rs, Hs	AR 0335
LILIOPSIDA Batsch				
Hydrocharitaceae Juss.				
<i>Hydrilla verticillata</i> (L. f.) Royle	Jhangi	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0407
Arecaceae Bercht. & J. Presl				
<i>Areca catechu</i> L.	Supari	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0394
<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Tal	Tree	Rs, Cs	AR 0312
<i>Calamus guruba</i> Buch.-Ham. ex Mart.	Bet	Climber	Rs, Cs	AR 0504
<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	Narikel	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0032
<i>Nypa fruticans</i> Wurmb	Golpata	Shrub	Wl, Cs	AR 0232
<i>Phoenix paludosa</i> Roxb.	Hetal	Tree	Cs, Wl	AR 0272
<i>P. sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb.	Khejur	Tree	Rs, Cs	AR 0307
Pandanaeae R.Br.				
<i>Pandanus amaryllifolius</i> Roxb.	Polao pata	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0171
<i>P. foetidus</i> Roxb.	Keya kanta	Shrub	Wl, Cs	AR 0248
Araceae Juss.				
<i>Alocasia macrorrhizos</i> (L.) G. Don	Mankochu	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0345

<i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (L.) Schott	Kachu	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0153
<i>Cryptocoryne retrospiralis</i> (Roxb.) Kunth	Kelakachu	Herb	Cs, Wl	AR 0352
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	Khudi pana	Herb	Wtl, Rs	AR 0455
<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Topapana	Herb	Wtl	AR 0047
<i>Xanthosoma violaceum</i> Schott	Dudkachu	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0111
Commelinaceae Mirb.				
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Kanshira	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0348
<i>C. longifolia</i> Lam.	-	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0479
<i>Murdannia nudiflora</i> (L.) Brenan	Kanduli	Herb	Fl	AR 0309
Flagellariaceae Dumort.				
<i>Flagellaria indica</i> L.	Banchanda	Climber	Wl, Cs	AR 0485
Cyperaceae Juss.				
<i>Cyperus articulatus</i> L.	Sondhaghas	Herb	Wtl, Af	AR 0192
<i>C. brevifolius</i> (Rottb.) Hassk.	Sedge	Herb	Wtl, Af, Rs	AR 0144
<i>C. compressus</i> L.	Chach	Herb	Wtl, Af	AR 0467
<i>C. cuspidatus</i> Kunth	Sedge	Herb	Af, Wtl	AR 0226
<i>C. difformis</i> L.	Behua ghas	Herb	Cs, Af	AR 0117
<i>C. eragrostis</i> Lam.	Chatidora	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0414
<i>C. exaltatus</i> Retz.	Sedge	Herb	Af, Rs, Cs	AR 0191
<i>C. imbricatus</i> Retz.	Sedge	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0416
<i>C. lucidus</i> R. Br.	Sedge	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0121
<i>C. malaccensis</i> Lam.	Sedge	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0492
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	Muthagass	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0500
<i>C. squarrosus</i> L.	Sedge	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0168
<i>Eleocharis geniculata</i> (L.) Roem. & Schult.	Joraghasi	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0443
<i>Fimbristylis acuminata</i> Vahl	-	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0374
<i>F. dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	Fimbristylis	Herb	Rs, Af, Fl	AR 0268
<i>F. disticha</i> Boeckeler	-	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0415
<i>F. ferruginea</i> (L.) Vahl	Rusty sedge	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0349
<i>F. ovata</i> (Burm. f.) J. Kern	-	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0254
<i>Fuirena umbellata</i> Rottb.	Umbrella sedges	Herb	Af	AR 0386
<i>Kyllinga nemoralis</i> (J.R. Forst. & G. Forst.) Dandy ex Hutch. & Dalziel	Sada kadamghas	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0367
<i>Pycnus polystachyos</i> (Rottb.) P. Beauv.	-	Herb	Fl, Af	AR 0056
<i>Schoenoplectus articulatus</i> (L.) Palla	Chechra	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0266
<i>S. supinus</i> (L.) Palla	-	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0370
<i>Scleria biflora</i> Roxb.	Sedge	Herb	Wl	AR 0030
Poaceae Barnhart				
<i>Axonopus compressus</i> (Sw.) P. Beauv.	Carpet grass	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0257
<i>Bambusa balcooa</i> Roxb.	Baiija Bash	Tree	Hs, Rs	AR 0371
<i>Chrysopogon aciculatus</i> (Retz.) Trin.	Premkata	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0081
<i>C. zizanioides</i> (L.) Roberty	Khas	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0211
<i>Coix lacryma jobi</i> L.	Tojbi dana	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0301
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Durbaghas	Herb	Rs, Hs, Af	AR 0423
<i>Digitaria sanguinalis</i> (L.) Scop.	Makunjill	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0184
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Shymaghas	Herb	Rs, Wtl	AR 0131
<i>E. polystachya</i> (Kunth) Hitchc.	-	Herb	Wtl	AR 0190
<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	Malankuri	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0167
<i>Eragrostis tenella</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Shada fulka	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0242
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Raeusch.	Ulu ghas	Herb	Rs, Hs	AR 0456
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	-	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0412
<i>Myriostachya nighiana</i> (Nees) Hook. f.	Dhansi	Herb	Cs, Wl	AR 0085
<i>Oplismenus burmanni</i> (Retz.) P. Beauv.	Kanguriya	Herb	Fl, Wtl	AR 0177
<i>O. compositus</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Boro pani kochu	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0310
<i>Oryza coarctata</i> Roxb.	Dhanshi	Herb	Cs, Wl	AR 0079
<i>O. sativa</i> L.	Dhan	Herb	Af, Cs	AR 0108
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i> P.J. Bergius	Hilo ghas	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0364

<i>P. distichum</i> L.	Gitlaghas	Herb	Af, Rs	AR 0060
<i>P. scrobiculatum</i> L.	Kodo	Herb	Af, Fl	AR 0427
<i>P. vaginatum</i> Sw.	Ginaghas	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0207
<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i> Schumach.	Nepiar ghas	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0298
<i>Phragmites karka</i> (Retz.) Trin. ex Steud.	Nol khagra	Herb	Cs, Rs	AR 0118
<i>Porteresia coarctata</i> (Roxb.) Tateoka	Uri	Herb	Cs, Wl	AR 0146
<i>Saccharum officinarum</i> L.	Akh	Herb	Af, Cs	AR 0182
<i>S. spontaneum</i> L.	Kashful	Herb	Cs, Af	AR 0273
<i>Urochloa distachyos</i> (L.) T.Q.Nguyen	Signalgrass	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0406
<i>U. mutica</i> (Forssk.) T.Q.Nguyen	Urochloa	Herb	Rs, Fl	AR 0029
<i>Zoysia matrella</i> (L.) Merr.	Manila ghas	Herb	Cs, Wl	AR 0206
Musaceae Juss.				
<i>Musa acuminata</i> Colla	Kola	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0246
<i>M. paradisiaca</i> L.	Kola	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0148
Typhaceae Juss.				
<i>Typha elephantina</i> Roxb.	Hogla	Herb	Wtl, Wl, Cs	AR 0052
Zingiberaceae Martinov				
<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Halud	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0225
<i>C. zedoaria</i> (Christm.) Roscoe	Sothi	Herb	Rs, Af	AR 0048
<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	Ada	Herb	Hs, Af	AR 0221
Marantaceae R.Br.				
<i>Schumannianthus dichotomus</i> (Roxb.) Gagnep.	Patipata	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0441
Pontederiaceae Kunth				
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> (Mart.) Solms	Kochuripana	Herb	Wtl	AR 0363
Amaryllidaceae J. St.-Hil.				
<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	Onion	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0243
<i>A. sativum</i> L.	Garlic	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0488
<i>A. tuberosum</i> Rottler ex Sprengel	Garlic Chives	Herb	Af, Hs	AR 0315
<i>Crinum amoenum</i> Roxb.	Bonroshun	Herb	Wl, Af	AR 0137
<i>C. asiaticum</i> L.	Golroshun	Herb	Wl, Af	AR 0022
Asparagaceae Juss.				
<i>Cordyline fruticosa</i> (L.) A. Chev.	Agnishor	Shrub	Hs, Rs	AR 0239
<i>Dracaena sanderiana</i> Sander ex Mast.	Lucky Bamboo	Shrub	Hs, Wtl	AR 0054
Dioscoreaceae R.Br.				
<i>Dioscorea alata</i> L.	Momalu	Climber	Hs, Rs, Af	AR 0359
<i>D. bulbifera</i> L.	Matialu	Climber	Hs, Af	AR 0462
Orchidaceae Juss.				
<i>Dendrobium</i> sp.	Orchid	Herb	Hs, Rs	AR 0373

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, (2023-2024).

Notes: Habitat category: Cs= Canalside, Rs= Roadside, Hs= Homestead, Af= Agricultural field, Wl= Woodland, Fl= Fallow land, Wtl= Wetland, Sd= Sand dune; Representative specimens examined (RSE): AR= Ashrafur Rahman.

Among the life-form categories, the majority of 198 (51.7%) species are herbs, followed by 98 (25.59%), 45 (11.75%), and 42 (10.97%) species are represented as trees, shrubs, and climbers, respectively (Figure 2). The vascular plant species of the study area are observed to grow in different habitats including roadside, homestead, cultivated land or agricultural field, canal or river side, woodland, wetland, fallow land, beach or sand dune. Among these habitats, the highest percentage of species (34%) are found in the roadside habitat, followed by homestead (26%), agricultural field (13%), canal side and woodland (each of 8%), wetland and fallow land (each of 5%), while only 1% plant species are adapted in the sand dune habitat (Table 1).

Figure 2. Floristic Composition in Different Life-Form Categories of the Study Area

The average values of different diversity indices, including Simpson's, Shannon-Weiner, Margalef's, and McIntosh's diversity indices, varied in different representative sites as well as in three different seasons. Among the seasons, the average values varied from 0.59 to 0.81, 1.42 to 2.11, 1.67 to 2.39, and 0.38 to 0.61 for Simpson's, Shannon-Weiner, Margalef's, and McIntosh's indices, respectively (Figure 4). In different sites, the average diversity indices values are observed to range from 0.508 ± 0.250 to 0.815 ± 0.010 , 1.189 ± 0.505 to 2.094 ± 0.458 , 1.633 ± 0.132 to 2.704 ± 0.646 , and 0.331 ± 0.191 to 0.605 ± 0.122 for Simpson's, Shannon-Weiner, Margalef's, and McIntosh's indices, respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Site-Wise Average Species Diversity Indices Values of the Study Area

Representative Sites	Site-wise average diversity indices value			
	Simpson's index	Shannon-Wiener index	Margalef index	McIntosh index
Site-1	0.759±0.065	1.776±0.149	1.955±0.144	0.535±0.064
Site-2	0.815±0.010	1.942±0.113	1.841±0.603	0.598±0.015
Site-3	0.768±0.069	1.817±0.236	1.916±0.355	0.548±0.078
Site-4	0.580±0.358	1.422±0.840	2.085±0.508	0.380±0.282
Site-5	0.508±0.250	1.189±0.505	1.633±0.132	0.331±0.191
Site-6	0.518±0.281	1.279±0.684	1.887±0.228	0.346±0.240
Site-7	0.809±0.100	2.094±0.458	2.704±0.646	0.605±0.122
Site-8	0.748±0.152	1.842±0.597	2.361±0.970	0.538±0.161

Source: Researcher's Fieldwork, (2023-2024).

Discussion

The total number of 383 vascular plant species recorded by this study for the Char kukri Mukri mangrove ecosystem of Bhola district is higher than that of the finding of Uddin and Abiabdullah (2016) who reported 272 angiosperm species from the Char Kukri Mukri Wildlife Sanctuary. The present finding is also higher than those reported from the more or less similar coastal habitats of Bangladesh, like Kuakata National Park (265 species; Rahman *et al.*, 2017), Nijhum Dwip National Park (152 species; Uddin *et al.*,

2015), Saint Martin's Island (157 species; BOBLME, 2015), and Sonadia Island (138 species; Arefin *et al.*, 2017). In contrast, the present finding is lower than those of the findings of Barguna mangrove forest (532 species; Islam *et al.*, 2022), the Sundarban mangrove forest (528 species; Rahman *et al.*, 2015) and Sandwip Island (457 species; Sajib *et al.*, 2015) (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Season-Wise Average Species Diversity Indices Values of the Study Area

Figure 4. Species Composition in Different Coastal Ecosystems of Bangladesh Including the Present Study Area

The floristic diversity indices values of the present study reveal a poor to moderate levels ecosystem quality of the Char Kukri Mukri mangrove forest. The available data regarding the values of different diversity indices, especially the values of Simpson's and Shannon-Weiner diversity index were more or less corroborated with the findings of Rashid *et al.* (2008), Hossain (2013), Islam *et al.* (2016), and Islam (2023) where they conducted their experiment in the mangrove forest ecosystems of Bangladesh. In the present findings, the average Simpson's diversity index values are calculated as 0.69, 0.81, and 0.59 during

summer, monsoon, and winter seasons, respectively; on the other hand, Islam *et al.* (2016) recorded this value with a range between 0.79 and 0.88 from the Sundarbans mangrove forest. The average Shannon-Weiner diversity index values in the present study are found to range between 1.342 and 2.048 which is partially corroborated with the findings of Rashid *et al.* (2008) and Hossain (2013), who recorded this value ranged from 1.41 to 3.11, and 1.197 to 2.67, respectively for the Sundarbans mangrove forest in Bangladesh, as well as the finding of Islam 2023, who recorded this value ranged between 2.50 and 3.04 from the mangrove ecosystem of Barguna district. The upper limit of these findings is higher than that of the present finding. But Islam *et al.* (2016) recorded this value ranging from 3.30 to 3.91 in the Sundarbans mangrove forest ecosystem of Bangladesh, which is in conflict with the current findings.

Conclusion

The present research investigation concluded that the study area exhibits a semi-evergreen planted mangrove ecosystem with diverse micro-habitats, where harboring a heterogeneous assemblage of vascular plants of both mangrove and non-mangrove species. Based on the species diversity index value, the present study indicates a poor to moderate level of ecosystem quality but seems to highly potential for the plantation of selected mangrove, non-mangrove native species. However, this coastal mangrove ecosystem is highly dynamic and provides a wide range of ecosystem goods and services. But unfortunately, this productive and protective ecosystem is gradually degraded due to perturbation caused by multifarious anthropogenic activities, such as- habitat destruction, deforestation, overexploitation of forest resources, timber and firewood collection, over grassing, infrastructure development, introduction of invasive plant species, unplanned tourism, pollution, as well as the frequent occurrence of natural disasters like cyclones, tidal surges, and tropical storms, river bank erosion by tidal waves, etc. are recognized as the severe threats for this mangrove ecosystem. In addition to the lack of proper management and public awareness are the critical threats for the flora and habitats of the mangrove ecosystems of the Char Kukri Mukri Island. As a result, the existing ecosystem has been gradually lost its potential biodiversity and becoming more vulnerable. In spite of different climatic and non-climatic threats, the study area is still floristically quite good than that of previously conducted studies on some coastal ecosystems of the country.

The present study provides a basic information on the vascular flora and relevant threats causing the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem quality. This information might be useful in undertaking appropriate master plan for sustainable conservation of biodiversity, coastal habitats and socio-economic development of this disaster-prone area. The authors highly recommend adopting a master plan for minimizing the adverse impacts of climate change and anthropogenic interferences. It is strongly suggested to ensure regular monitoring of the flora and habitats, and implementation of appropriate measures for the conservation of the biodiversity of this Island.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Ahmed, Z. U., Begum, Z. N. T., Hassan, M. A., Khondker, M., Kabir, S. M. H., Ahmad, M., Ahmed, A. T. A., Rahman, A. K. A., & Haque, E. U. (Eds.). (2008-2009). *Encyclopedia of Flora and Fauna of Bangladesh* (Vols. 6-8 & 12). Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Dhaka.
- Ahmed, Z. U., Hassan, M. A., Begum, Z. N. T., Khondker, M., Kabir, S. M. H., Ahmad, M., & Ahmed, A. T. A. (Eds.). (2009). *Encyclopedia of Flora and Fauna of Bangladesh* (Vols. 9-10). Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Dhaka.
- Arefin, M. K., Rahman, M. M., Uddin, M. Z., & Hassan, M. A. (2011). Angiosperm flora of Satchari National Park, Habiganj, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 18(2), 117-140. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v18i2.9298>
- Arefin, M. S., Hossain, M. K., & Hossain, M. A. (2017). Plant diversity of Sonadia Island—an ecologically critical area of south-east Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 24(1), 107-116. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v24i1.33037>
- Ashrafuzzaman, M., & Sarwar, A. K. M. G. (2021). Addition to the angiospermic flora of Bangladesh: Family Acanthaceae. *Journal of Bangladesh Agricultural University*, 19(4), 447-455. <https://doi.org/10.5455/JBAU.131566>
- Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. (2011). *Monthly Statistical Bulletin, December 2011*. Statistics Division, Ministry of Planning, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh.
- Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics. (2021). *Statistical Yearbook Bangladesh, 2020* (40th ed.). Statistics & Informatics Division (SID), Ministry of Planning, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- Barker, P. (2001). *A technical manual for vegetation monitoring*. Resource Management and Conservation, Department of Primary Industries, Water and Environment, Hobart.
- Bhuiyan, M. A. R., Hossain, G. M., & Rahman, M. M. (2025). Soil physico-chemical properties of the Char Kukri-Mukri mangrove forest in Bhola District, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Ecology and Environmental Sciences*, 7(3), 95-101.
- BOBLME. (2015). *Saint Martin's biological survey report (Fauna and Flora), Bangladesh*.
- Braun-Blanquet, J. (1932). *Plant sociology: The study of plant communities*. McGraw-Hill.
- Bridson, D., & Forman, L. (1989). *The herbarium handbook*. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew.
- Cain, S. A. (1938). The species-area curve. *American Midland Naturalist*, 19, 573-581.
- Cronquist, A. (1988). *The evolution and classification of flowering plants* (2nd ed.). The New York Botanical Garden, Bronx, NY.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO). (2007). *The world's mangroves 1980-2005: A thematic study prepared in the framework of the Global Forest Resources Assessment 2005*. Rome, Italy: FAO.
- Giesen, W., Wulffraat, S., Zieren, M., & Scholten, L. (2007). *Mangrove guidebook for Southeast Asia*. FAO & Wetlands International; Dharmasarn Co., Ltd.
- Green, M. J. B. (1990). *IUCN directory South Asian Protected Areas* (1st ed.). IUCN.

- Haque, A. K. M. K., Khan, S. A., Uddin, S. N., & Shetu, S. S. (2018). An annotated checklist of the angiospermic flora of Rajkandi Reserve Forest of Moulvibazar, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 25(2), 187-207. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v25i2.39525>
- Hassler, M. (1994–2025). *World Plants: Synonymic checklist and distribution of the world flora* (Version 25.08, last update August 18, 2025). Retrieved from <http://www.worldplants.de>
- Hooker, J. D. (1872-1897). *The Flora of British India* (Vols. 1-7). L. Reeve & Co., Ashford, Kent, UK.
- Hossain, G. M. (2013). *Ecosystem health status assessment of the Sundarbans mangrove forest in Bangladesh* (Doctoral dissertation). Jahangirnagar University, Savar, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
- Hossain, G. M., Khan, S. A., Rahim, M. A., Rahman, M. S., & Islam, K. M. N. (2021). Floristic composition of the coastal district Satkhira, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 28(1), 97-124. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v28i1.54211>
- Hossain, G. M., Khan, S. A., Rahman, M. S., & Rahim, M. D. (2020). New records of three species and a variety of angiosperms for Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 27(2), 251-260. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v27i2.50665>
- Hossain, G. M., Khan, S. A., Shetu, S. S., Rahman, M. S., Ahmed, F. A., & Ali, M. H. (2022). Floristic survey of vascular plants in coastal district Bagerhat of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 29(1), 43-78. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v29i1.60448>
- Hossain, G. M., Shetu, S. S., & Khan, S. A. (2023). Four new records for the vascular flora of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 30(1), 21-30. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v30i1.67031>
- Islam, M. A., Rahman, M. M., & Hossain, G. M. (2024). Floristic composition and phytodiversity status of Bangabandhu Jamuna Eco-Park, Sirajganj, Bangladesh. *International Journal of Science Research in Biological Sciences*, 11(5), 1-12.
- Islam, M. R., Hossain, G. M., & Rahman, M. M. (2022). An annotated checklist of the vascular flora of coastal mangrove ecosystems of Barguna District, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 29(2), 403-429. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v29i2.63536>
- Islam, M. R., Uddin, M. Z., & Hassan, M. A. (2009). An assessment of the angiospermic flora of Ramgarh Upazila of Khagrachhari district, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 16(2), 115-140. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v16i2.3925>
- Islam, S. I., Feroz, S. M., Ahmed, Z. U., Chowdhuri, A. H., Khan, R. I., & Al-Mamun, A. (2016). Species richness and diversity of the floristic composition of the Sundarbans mangrove reserve forest, Bangladesh in relation to spatial habitats and salinity. *Malaysian Forester*, 79(12), 7-38.
- Junaid, Z. B. (2018). Analysis of WeChat by walk-through method. *SocioInt J.*, 2(6), 709-713. <https://doi.org/10.15406/sij.2018.02.00124>
- Khan, M. S. (1977). Onagraceae. In M. S. Khan (Ed.), *Flora of Bangladesh* (Vol. 6, pp. 1-10). Bangladesh National Herbarium, BARC, Dhaka.
- Khan, M. S., & Huq, A. M. (2001). The vascular flora of Chunati Wildlife Sanctuary in south Chittagong. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Khan, S. A., & Rahman, M. S. (2025). Three new records of angiosperms for Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 32(1), 115-122. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v32i1.82399>
- Khan, S. A., Hossain, G. M., Shetu, S. S., Rahim, M. A., Islam, M. S., Ahmed, F. A., & Fairy, R. H. (2021b). A preliminary taxonomic study on the flora of Rangpur District, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 28(2), 329-365. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v28i2.57131>

- Khan, S. A., Sultana, S., Hossain, G. M., Shetu, S. S., & Rahim, M. A. (2021a). Floristic composition of Jahangirnagar University Campus — a semi-natural area of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 28(1), 27-60. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v28i1.54207>
- Khanam, R., Khan, S. A., & Rahim, M. A. (2020 a & b). Angiosperms in Narsingdi district of Bangladesh: Class Magnoliopsida. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 27(1), 153-271. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v27i1.47576>
- Kramer, K. U., & Green, P. S. (1990). Pteridophytes and gymnosperms. In K. Kubitzki (Ed.), *The families and genera of vascular plants* (Vol. 1). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-19740-4>
- Margalef, D. R. (1957). Information theory in ecology. *Memorias de la Real Academia de Ciencias y Artes de Barcelona*, 32, 374-559.
- McIntosh, R. P. (1967). An index of diversity and the relations of certain concepts to diversity. *Ecology*, 48(3), 392-404. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1932674>
- Nishat, A., Huq, S. M. I., Barua, S. P., Reza, A. H. M. A., & Khan, M. A. S. (Eds.). (2002). *Bio-ecological zones of Bangladesh*. IUCN Bangladesh Country Office, Dhaka.
- Pichi Sermolli, R. E. G. (1977). Tentamen pteridophytorum genera in taxonomicum ordinem redigendi. *Webbia*, 31(1), 313–512. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00837792.1977.10670077>
- POWO. (2025). *Plants of the World Online*. Facilitated by the Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Retrieved from <https://powo.science.kew.org>
- Prain, D. (1903a). *Bengal plants* (Vols. 1–2). (Reprinted 1963). Botanical Survey of India, Calcutta.
- Prain, D. (1903b). Flora of Sundarbans. *Records of the Botanical Survey of India*, 2(4), 231–270.
- Rahaman, M. A., Rahman, M. A., & Uddin, M. Z. (2017). Diversity of angiosperm flora of Kuakata National Park, Patuakhali District, Bangladesh. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Science*, 43(2), 143–159.
- Rahman, M. S., Hossain, G. M., Khan, S. A., & Uddin, S. N. (2015). An annotated checklist of the vascular plants of the Sundarbans mangrove forest of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 22(1), 17–41. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v22i1.23862>
- Rahman, M. S., Khan, S. A., Hossain, G. M., Islam, K. K., & Hoque, M. A. (2023). Three new records of Lauraceae for Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 30(1), 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v30i1.67046>
- Rani, P., Khan, S. A., Uddin, S. N., Rahim, M. A., & Shetu, S. S. (2024). Three new records of Lythraceae in the flora of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 31(1), 15–24. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v31i1.74374>
- Rashid, S. H., & Mia, M. M. K. (2001). Angiospermic flora of Madhupur National Park, Tangail, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 8(2), 63–82.
- Rashid, S. H., Böcker, R., Hossain, A. B. M. E., & Khan, S. A. (2008). Undergrowth species diversity of Sundarban mangrove forest (Bangladesh) in relation to salinity. *Berichte des Instituts für Landschafts- und Pflanzenökologie der Universität Hohenheim*, 41, 41–56.
- Raunkiaer, C. (1934). *The life forms of plants and statistical plant geography*. Oxford University Press.
- Roxburgh, W. (1814). *Hortus Bengalensis* (num. nud.). Boerhaave Press, Leiden.

- Roy, G. K., & Khan, S. A. (2020a). Preliminary taxonomic study on homestead flora of four districts of Bangladesh: Magnoliopsida. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 27(1), 37–65. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v27i1.47577>
- Roy, G. K., & Khan, S. A. (2020b). Preliminary taxonomic study on homestead flora of four districts of Bangladesh: Liliopsida (Monocotyledons) and Pteridophyta. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 27(2), 407–425. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v27i2.50679>
- Sajib, N. H., Uddin, S. B., & Pasha, M. K. (2015). Angiospermic plant diversity of Sandwip Island, Chittagong, Bangladesh. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Science*, 41(2), 133–153.
- Shannon, C. E. (1948). A mathematical theory of communication. *Bell System Technical Journal*, 27(3), 379–423. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1538-7305.1948.tb01338.x>
- Shetu, S. S., Hossain, G. M., Khan, S. A., & Rahim, M. A. (2022). An inventory of vascular flora of Lamai Hills and their adjacent areas of Cumilla District, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 29(2), 203–240. <https://doi.org/10.3329/bjpt.v29i2.63527>
- Shetu, S. S., Khan, S. A., & Uddin, S. N. (2018). Checklist of angiosperms extant in Mirpur area of Dhaka City. *Jahangirnagar University Journal of Biological Sciences*, 7(2), 47–64. <https://doi.org/10.3329/jujbs.v7i2.40746>
- Siddiqui, K. U., Islam, M. A., Ahmed, Z. U., Begum, Z. N. T., Hassan, M. A., Khondker, M., Rahman, M. M., Kabir, S. M. H., Ahmad, M., Ahmed, A. T. A., Rahman, A. K. T., & Haque, E. U. (Eds.). (2007). *Encyclopedia of flora and fauna of Bangladesh* (Vols. 5 & 11). Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Dhaka.
- Simpson, E. H. (1949). Measurement of diversity. *Nature*, 163(4148), 688. <https://doi.org/10.1038/163688a0>
- Singh, H. B., & Subramaniam, B. (2008). *Field manual on herbarium techniques*. National Institute of Science Communication and Information Resources.
- Sultana, M. (2012). Taxonomic and ethnobotanical studies on the angiospermic flora of Patuakhali District in Bangladesh (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Dhaka.
- Tabassum, R. (2015). Angiospermic flora of Gazipur District, Bangladesh (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Dhaka.
- The Angiosperm Phylogeny Group. (2016). An update of the Angiosperm Phylogeny Group classification for the orders and families of flowering plants: APG IV. *Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society*, 181(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1111/boj.12385>
- The Plant List. (2013). *The Plant List: A working list of all plant species* (Version 1.1). Retrieved April 15, 2021, from <http://www.theplantlist.org>
- Tropicos. (2025). *Tropicos.org*. Missouri Botanical Garden. Retrieved August 2025, from <http://www.tropicos.org>
- Uddin, M. Z., & Abiabdullah, M. (2016). Taxonomic study on the angiosperms of Char Kukri-Mukri Wildlife Sanctuary, Bhola District. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Science*, 42(2), 153–168.
- Uddin, M. Z., Hassan, M. A., & Khan, M. S. (2003). An annotated checklist of angiospermic flora of Rema Kalenga Wildlife Sanctuary (Habiganj) in Bangladesh IIa: Magnoliopsida (Dicots). *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 10(1), 79–94.
- Uddin, M. Z., Kibria, M. G., & Hassan, M. A. (2015). Assessment of angiosperm plant diversity of Nijhum Dweep, Bangladesh. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Science*, 41(1), 19–32.

- Uddin, S. N., & Hassan, M. A. (2018). *Vascular flora of Chittagong and the Chittagong Hill Tracts* (Vols. 1–3). Bangladesh National Herbarium, Dhaka.
- Uddin, S. N., Khan, M. S., Hassan, M. A., & Alam, M. K. (1998). An annotated checklist of angiospermic flora of Sitapahar at Kaptai in Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 5(1), 13–46.
- Wu, Z. Y., & Raven, P. H. (Eds.). (1994–2001). *Flora of China* (Vols. 8, 15–18, 24). Missouri Botanical Garden Press, St. Louis.
- Wu, Z. Y., Raven, P. H., & Hong, D. Y. (Eds.). (1999–2013). *Flora of China* (Vols. 2–7, 9–14, 19–23, 25). Missouri Botanical Garden Press, St. Louis.

